

MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH WORKS CARRIED OUT IN THE PROCESS OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article presents the continuity of the scientific research work carried out in the process of continuing professional development.*

Keywords: *continuous education, modern, scientific research, intellectuality, communicativeness, competence.*

Continuous education models in the world are aimed at ensuring the quality and competitiveness of the continuous education system by increasing the continuous professional skills of teachers based on the andragogic approach, improving the mechanisms of teaching them in a general secondary educational institution, in a real educational environment, aimed at developing methodological competence in this process. is being implemented. In the declaration of development until 2030 adopted at the World Education Forum held in the Republic of Korea, "creating opportunities for quality education throughout life" [55], increasing the level of methodological training in the professional activities of primary school teachers, systematic work is being carried out to ensure the development of the education sector. various models and technologies of continuous professional development (continuous professional development). In particular, Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [3; p. 48-49] defined the priority directions aimed at improving the education system. In particular, special attention is being paid to the issues of quality organization of public education institutions and continuous improvement of qualifications in the direction of the decree called "fair social policy, development of human capital".

In the process of continuous professional development, the introduction of the system for the development of methodological competence of primary school teachers will provide mechanisms for the continuous updating of the professional knowledge, skills and abilities of public education workers, and the methodological training necessary to ensure the quality of professional development. including introduction. putting it into practice with modern requirements, it serves as an important resource for improving and developing the system of continuous professional development of public education workers.

B.A.Supieva demonstrated the technologies of improving the creative activity of the trainees in the context of "VUCA-world" narratives and demanded the pedagogical possibilities of using the "Metodium" project to improve the creativity of the trainees. Approaches such as the improvement of the "generation theory" as a teaching methodology and the continuous training system, and the formation of pedagogical marketing are reflected.

Recommendations for the development of modern technologies of continuous professional development of elementary school teachers were created in the scientific research of M.J.Shodieva in the process of professional development based on the acmeological approach. In addition, the personal, social, general professional and special components of the primary school teacher have

been improved. Based on the principle of "lifelong learning", the model of continuous professional development and the algorithm of applying technologies of continuous professional development of primary school teachers have been improved based on the integration of traditional and electronic training.

N.A. Valikhonova's opinion on the content, form, methods and tools of the development of information and communication competence of primary school teachers during the training process, as well as the philosophical, pedagogical, psychological analysis of this process, the model of the development of information and communication competence of the primary school teacher conducted Accordingly, in his scientific and research work, he demonstrated the creation of electronic educational materials for educational processes, didactic material for infographics, multimedia electronic tests. Technologies for the development of information and communication competence of the primary school teacher are emphasized on the educational use of Internet educational resources, programs and software tools.

In the research of I.I.Hojiboev, it was noted that the training course for public education staff was effectively organized at the level of developing the professional competence of pedagogues in the dynamic formation of qualities such as "intellectuality", "sociality" in students. manifestation of the motive of "pursuit of success".

In order to study M.B.Shodmonova in the process of continuous professional development, it is envisaged to improve modern technologies for the development of professional training of native language teachers. In addition, the training model of native language and literature teachers is based on the requirements of modern Andragogy, and the didactic implementation of the use of technology has been improved. Pedagogical capabilities of the native language and literature teacher were identified with the help of distance learning technologies.

In the research work of Sh.Boboyorov, the philosophical, pedagogical and psychological possibilities of self-development competence of teachers in the process of professional development, the model of teacher's self-development in the process of professional development, and the stages of designing have been improved. In addition, in the process of continuous professional development, the teacher's self-development has been improved based on the identification of pedagogical opportunities such as motivational, problem-solving, mutual assistance, critical and creative approach, independent decision-making.

The principles of improving the competence of self-development of teachers in the process of professional development in Sh.Boboyorov's research work:

- Technologyization of education
- Individualization of education
- Teachers' pursuit of the goal
- Activity
- Possession of reasonable motivation.

Criteria: motivational, valuable, creative, cognitive, reflexive.

For the purpose of D.A.Khidoyatova's research, suggestions and recommendations have been developed on the improvement of the skills of Uzbek language teachers who teach in Russian in schools based on the improvement of the interactive teaching model. Also, tasks such as monitoring development indicators, interactive learning model, technologies for creating new modern interactive methods and determining the mechanisms of their use were performed.

M.Yu.Makhmudov is aimed at improving the system of improving the qualifications of public education workers based on an innovative-variational approach. Philosophical, pedagogical and psychological possibilities were analyzed based on the innovation-variational approach during the training course. In addition, the socio-pedagogical model of variable technologies has been improved in the qualification training system and developed on the basis of ensuring the harmony of need-based differentiated principles on the basis of competence acmeological, modern andragogic criteria.

T.T.Shoymardonov noted that the process of professional development consists of the introduction of the electronic methodical system of teacher retraining and monitoring of their professional activities, theoretical justification and implementation. In particular, an electronic methodical system of formation of monitoring of professional activities of personnel retraining and qualification improvement has been developed. An electronic system platform for monitoring professional activity was put into practice. As a result of the research, it can be concluded that there is a special emphasis on summarizing and spreading the experience of teachers who combine knowledge and skills related to the development of continuous professional activity and implement technological aspects of the educational process skillfully and actively introduce innovations. Attention is given to the practice of primary schools, therefore teachers, in their opinion, their important professional qualities can be achieved through the introduction of vocational education systems aimed at the development of ethno-cultural competences.

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